

Analysis of Value Addition among Cashew Nuts Processors in Southwestern, Nigeria

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Abstract

Despite Nigeria being the hub of cashew production, processing and value addition activities remain at its lowest ebb. This study therefore analyze value addition among cashew nuts processors in Southwest, Nigeria. Multistage sampling technique was used to select 43 cashew processors. A Double-Log Regression Model and One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyses the data. The study revealed that in first year (2019) result, the coefficient of gender was positive and significant at 10% level. Weather variation is statistically significant at 10% level of confidence. Processing experience is another key factor that contribute to value addition of cashew nut in the study area. The cost of labour is significant at 1% and negatively related to value addition. For the year 2020, value addition of cashew nut producers reduces by 0.3306. Meanwhile the coefficient of weather variation, market price, drying labour space, distance to processing unit and years of experience showed positive relationship with value addition of cashew nut processors in the year 2020. It was concluded that in2019, an increase in male processors will lead to increase in value addition of cashew nut. Increase in weather variation will result to increase in value addition of cashew nuts through processors by 0.1834. Increase in change in weather will result to increase value addition. The result indicated that an extra unit cost of labour will reduce value addition of cashew. In 2020, this indicated that most cashew nut processors have over utilized labour and addition cost on labour will negatively affect their expected value addition. Therefore, more male individuals should engage in processing of cashew. cashew processors should manage weather variation properly and they should also optimize the cost of labour.

Keywords: *Cashew, cost of labour, processor, value chain and weather variation*

1. INTRODUCTION

More attention has been given to the cashew crop in the last decades because it is a highly-valued commodity with rising global market value (FAOSTAT, 2023). The expectation is that the market will remain strong for a long time to come due to the huge global market potential for tradability of high-value cashew by-products, like cashew nutshell liquid (CNSL), cashew butter, cashew shell cake, and broken nuts. Interestingly, the federal government trade policy of liberalizing export crops has had a considerable impact on the pricing and supply of unprocessed cashew nuts in Nigeria (CBN, 2020). Nigeria still offers one of the cheapest sources of raw cashew nuts. Nigerian nut has constantly been used in Indian and Vietnamese cashew industries and more recently, added substantially to the Brazilian market.

The exports of the non-value-added products (raw nuts), as well as low export of value-added products (e.g., kernels), have been the major constraints to the development of the cashew value chain industry in Nigeria (CBN, 2020) resulting in poor foreign exchange earnings and loss of job opportunities. Nigeria still earns the least international premium from raw cashew nuts. Even the neighbouring Republic of Benin earns 20 per cent price higher than Nigeria (CBN, 2020). Small nuts, peelability, and poor post-harvest handling have been identified by USAID-Nigeria as the contributing factors to this low price. For instance, numerous flesh apples and nuts waste away in several cashew farms, simply because most of these producers lack the competence to sufficiently cashew into more acceptable products for consumption as well as marketing at both local and international markets. FAOSTAT (2023) reported that 40-50 percent losses in cashew produce are attributed to poor post-harvest handling. This wastage leads to losses of livelihood and employment opportunities. No matter the case, Nigeria still has the potential to improve its price to at least the same level as her West African neighbours through value addition. Value-addition can create opportunities for small to medium scale processors to take advantage of the growing demand for cashew products to create market niches (SBM Intelligence, 2016).

Cashew remains a major export crop and source of livelihood to numerous smallholder farmers in the middle belt and southeastern zones of Nigeria (Salau *et al.*, 2016). However, despite Nigeria being the hub of cashew production, processing and value addition activities remain at its lowest ebb. This is seen in the absence of the major large-scale cashew processing firms in the country.

Objective:

- analyze the factors influencing the value addition among cashew nuts processors in the study area

Hypothesis of the Study:

H₀: There is no significant difference in value addition to cashew nut among cashew processors in the study area

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Southwestern, Nigeria. The zone was chosen because of its status as one of the major cashew growing areas in the country and according to Adeoye *et al.*, 2013, the prospect for value addition is promising due to the presence of emerging processing industries. The zone is made up of six states namely Lagos, Oyo, Ogun, Osun, Ekiti and Ondo States and it falls on latitude 6° to the North and latitude 4° to the south while it is marked by longitude 4° to the west and 6° to the east. It is bounded in the North by Kogi and Kwara states, in the east by Edo and Delta states in the south by Atlantic Ocean and in the west by Republic of Benin.

The zone is characterized by a tropical climate with distinct dry season between November and March; a wet season between April and October. The Southwest Nigeria covers about 114,271 kilometres square land area. The total population is 27,581,992 and predominantly agrarian. Agriculture forms the predominant occupation of the populace alongside other vocations like trading, crafts, fishing and agro-processing among others. Major food crops grown in the area include cassava, yam and maize while cash crops include cocoa, kolanut, cashew, oilpalm, orange and mango (Oduwole, 2004).

The study was conducted in two Southwestern States, Nigeria. Oyo and Ogun states were considered for the study among cashew processing areas in Southwestern States, Nigeria. Oyo state is purposively selected based on its active production of cashew in order of importance in Southwestern states of Nigeria (Akanni *et al.*, 2011; Ezeagu, 2002). Of the Southwestern states, according to Chemonics (2002), Oyo State has the largest hectareage under cultivation compared with Ekiti, Osun, Ondo and Ogun States. Oyo State gives a good representative of three main ecological zones (i.e the rainforest, guinea and derived savannah) found in the Southwestern States of Nigeria while Ogun in the other hand was chosen because of location of cashew processing firms in the area. Ogun State is one the fastest-growing States in Southwestern Nigeria because of its conducive environment to accommodate investment opportunities. The state lies in the rainforest vegetation belt of Nigeria in the tropics along latitude 6° 20' South and 7° 58' North and longitude 2° 40' West and 4° 35' East along the Greenwich Meridian. Ogun state has a land area

of 16,409.28 km², this is less than 2 percent of the country's landmass and a population of about 3,728,098 which is approximately 2.70 percent of Nigeria's population (Olaoye *et al.*, 2007)

Figure 2: Map of Nigeria Showing the Study Area (source: Popoola, 2020)

The respondents of the study are cashew processors in Oyo and Ogun States. However, purposive and random sampling techniques was used to select cashew processors. Obafemi Owode in Ogun State was purposively selected because of corporate cashew processing firms located in the area. A total of 30 processing industries from Obafemi-owode Local Government Ogun State was randomly selected. Apart from this, 13 local cashew processing firms were purposively selected from Ogbomoso North LGA in Oyo State. The total sample size for the study is 43 cashew processors. They were randomly selected from the list of cashew processors in each of the community. All the respondents randomly selected were selected proportionate to the size of the processors in the communities (Table 1) which formed the respective sampling frames in each chosen community randomly selected. The proportionate factor that was used is Yamane formula (1967):

The Yamane formula is expressed as;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2} \tag{1}$$

n= sample size

N= finite population

e= limit of tolerable error (0.05)

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents According to Local Governments

State	LGAs	Communities	Cashew Processors	
			Sampling Frame	Sample Size
Oyo	Ogbomoso North	Ogbomoso	15	13
Ogun	Obafemi Owode	Ibafo Mowe	13 20	12 18
Total	2	3	48	43

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The various value addition practiced by the cashew processors in the study area using double log regression model analysis

Model specification

A Double-Log Regression Model

A Double-log Model is a model where both the dependent variable (Y) and the right hand side variables (i.e., X₁, ..., X_k) have been transformed by the natural logarithm. This was used to estimate the factors that influence value addition among the actors in the value chain and is stated as follows:

Double log functional form

$$\ln Y = \ln a + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + \dots + \mu \tag{2}$$

Where; a = intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_{13}$ = regression coefficients estimated

ln denotes the natural logarithm.

e = Error term

Three separate regression analyses were carried out for processors for the three years, one for 2019, 2020 and the other for 2021 with the model expressed implicitly as follows:

Y = value addition of each actor for 2019/2020/2021.

X₁= Age (years)

X₂ = Marital status (married = 1 otherwise =0)

X₃= Years of Education (years)

X₄= Level of production/marketing/processing

X₅= Farm size (hectare)

X₆= Contract farming (dummy)

X₇ = Years of experience (years)

X₈ = Gender (dummy)

X₉ = Credit access (access = 1 otherwise =0)

X₁₀ = Weather variation (1=yes, 0= otherwise)

X₁₁ = Harvesting method & time (prompt harvesting = 1, otherwise 0)

X₁₂ = Household size (Number of people living and feeding from the same pot)

X₁₃= Drying slab or space (dummy)

X₁₄= Cost of labour (Naira)

X₁₅= Storage facility (dummy)

X₁₆= Market outlets (dummy)

X₁₇= Processing facilities (dummy)

X₁₈= Distance to farm (km)

X₁₉= Distance to market (km)

X₂₀= Distance to processing unit (km)

One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for independent groups is used to test whether the group means for a specific dependent variable differ significantly after exposing each group to a unique level of a single factor or independent variable (Norton, *et al.*, 1985). The tool is used to detect a difference in means of 3 or more independent groups. It compares the means of the samples or groups in order to make inferences about the population means. In this study, Anova was used to test for the hypothesis. This was used to estimate the difference in value addition to cashew nut among the various value chain actors in the study area.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Value Addition among the Cashew Nut Processors

Result presented on Table 2 indicated the estimates of the factors that influences value addition of cashew nut processors in the study area. In the first year of consideration – 2019, about 10 variables were statistically significant and these include: gender, years of processing experience, weather variation, market price, drying labour space, cost of labour, storage facility, distance to processing unit, market outlet and processing facilities. For the year 2020, all these variables were also significant except gender and processing facilities. This same trend was observed with the result in 2021. From the first year (2019) result, the coefficient of gender was positive and significant at 10% level; this signifies that increase in male processors will lead to increase in value addition of cashew nut. Processing cashew is quite laborious and it requires a lot of energy and commitment, so more men found themselves in this work more than their female counterparts. Though significant number of women are also involved in this.

Weather variation is statistically significant at 10% level of confidence. This implies increase in weather variation will result to increase in value addition of cashew nuts through processors by 0.1834. Processing experience is another key factor that contribute to value addition of cashew nut in the study area. From the results, this variable contributes about 16% increase to value addition when there is increase in the year of processing experience. The result indicated that for a unit increase in processors experience, there will be about 16% increase in value addition of cashew nut among processors in the study area. Processing cashew nut in time of higher humidity will take

a longer time than when the nuts are dried, it was evidence that increase in change in weather will result to increase value addition.

Another key factor to value addition among cashew nut processors is the market price of the commodity. With the result on Table 2, the study showed that increase in market price will lead to increase in value addition of cashew nut through processors by 0.2654. The cost of labour is significant at 1% and negatively related to value addition. It means cost of labour retrogress value addition of cashew nut among processors. The result indicated that an extra unit cost of labour will reduce value addition of cashew. Storage facilities and market outlets are both positive and significant at 1%, indicating a unit increase in both will lead to increasing value addition of cashew nuts. Meanwhile, distance to processing unit and processing facility are both significant at 10% and positively related to value addition, which implies a unit increase in both will lead to increasing value addition of cashew nuts through cashew processors.

For the year 2020, the coefficient of weather variation, market price, drying labour space, cost of labour, storage facility, distance to processing unit and years of experience significantly influence value addition among the processors. As cost of labour, storage facility and market outlets were negative, it is an indication the these variable negatively affect value addition of cashew nut processors. With increase in cost of labour in for the year 2020 production cycle, value addition of cashew nut producers reduces by 0.3306; this indicated that most cashew nut processors have over utilized labour and addition cost on labour will negatively affect their expected value addition. Meanwhile the coefficient of weather variation, market price, drying labour space, distance to processing unit and years of experience showed positive relationship with value addition of cashew nut processors in the year 2020. The result simply depicts that increase in these variable will lead to increase in value addition of cashew nut processors in the study area.

Table 2: Factors Influencing Value Addition among the Cashew Nut Processors

Variables	2019			2020		
	Coefficient value	Std. dev.	t-value	Coefficient value	Std. dev.	t-value
Age	-	0.05	-1.45	-	0.00	-0.63
Gender	0.0727	02		0.0001	00	
Marital status	0.070	0.04	1.67*	0.047	0.05	0.91
Years of education	6	22		5	22	
Household size	0.019	0.04	0.45	0.017	0.05	0.33
Experience	4	33		7	36	
Years of experience	-	0.00	-1.01	-	0.00	-0.98
Credit access	0.0053	52		0.0063	64	
Weather variation	-	0.00	-0.09	-	0.00	-1.01
Market price	0.0003	34		0.0043	42	
Drying slab/space	-	0.00	-0.55	0.002	0.00	0.47
Cost of labour	0.0023	41		4	52	
Storage facility	0.358	0.14	2.43*	0.115	0.05	1.96*
Distance to processing unit	1	75	*	0	88	*
Market outlets	0.003	0.03	0.11	0.004	0.03	0.11
Processing facilities	4	22		2	99	
_cons	0.183	0.10	1.74*	0.259	0.13	1.99*
	4	54		9	05	*
	0.265	0.11	2.29*	0.335	0.14	2.34*
	4	59	*	2	35	*
	0.142	0.05	2.38*	0.176	0.07	2.38*
	6	98	*	2	40	*
	-	0.10	-	-	0.13	-
	0.2827	65	2.65***	0.3306	18	2.51**
		0.06			0.07	
	0.1553	30	2.46***	0.1635	80	2.09**
	0.212	0.11	1.86*	0.278	0.14	1.98*
	3	39		4	09	*
		0.11			0.14	
	0.2812	73	2.40***	0.3074	52	2.12**
	0.172	0.09	1.87*		0.11	1.62*
	8	24		0.1849	43	
	0.603	0.62	0.97	-	0.76	-
	1	07		2.0010	81	2.61***

Source: Field Survey, 2023

*** Statistically significant at 1% level, ** Statistically significant at 5% level, * Statistically significant at 10% level

Test of hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant difference in value addition to cashew nut among the cashew processors

Test of the difference in value addition among the cashew nut processors

Findings in Table 3 reviewed significant differences ($F = 11.55$, $p = 0.0039$) in value addition of cashew nut processors in the study area. Given that the p-value is less than 0.05, thus the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, study concludes that there is a statistically significant difference in value addition to cashew nuts among the cashew processors in the study area.

Additionally, Bartlett's test for equal variances yielded a chi-squared value of 28.1100 with a p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the assumption of equal variances among groups does not hold, as the p-value is less than 0.05.

Table 3: Difference in Value Addition among Cashew Nut Processors in Value Chain

Variable	Sum of squares	Differences	Mean squares	F	Sig.	Decision
Between groups	2.0059e+11	2	1.0029e+11	6.39	0.0039	Significant
Within groups	6.2808e+11	40	1.5702e+10			
Total	8.2867e+11	42	1.9730e+10			
Bartlett's test for equal variances: $\chi^2(2) = 28.1100$						
Prob>	0.000					

Source: Field Survey, 2023

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It was concluded that in 2019, an increase in male processors will lead to increase in value addition of cashew nut. Increase in weather variation will result to increase in value addition of cashew nuts through processors by 0.1834. Increase in change in weather will result to increase value addition. The result indicated that an extra unit cost of labour will reduce value addition of cashew. In 2020, this indicated that most cashew nut processors have over utilized labour and addition cost on labour will negatively affect their expected value addition. Therefore, more male individuals should engage in processing of cashew. cashew processors should manage weather variation properly and they should also optimize the cost of labour.

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